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Electrochemical Investigation of Symmetric Aminoquinones

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Quinones have a wide range of valuable properties and potential applications in medicinal chemistry, materials science, optoelectronic devices, and batteries. Molecular redesign using different functional groups, like amines, can optimize their properties and prevent undesired side reactions. However, the synthesis of aminoquinones can be particularly challenging at times, and there is a need for simple and efficient routes to access these compounds without metal catalysts or halogenated starting materials. Here, we demonstrate the synthesis and electrochemical characterization of a series of aminoquinones derived from renewable sources, namely vanillin or 2-methoxyhydroquinone. We employ a series of primary and secondary amines, varying in their electronic situation as well as steric demand. Depending on the type of starting material, either the desired aminoquinone or the related Schiff-base adduct was obtained. The aminoquinones were further explored towards their stability at different pH values. At extreme pH values, the deeply colored aminoquinones decompose, accompanied by decolorization of the solutions within a few minutes (pH 14) or hours (pH 1). At intermediate pH values (3–8) the aminoquinones are stable upon storage in solution, where they feature a quasi-reversible redox chemistry and fast, diffusion limited kinetics.

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Redox reactions hold immense significance not only in the realm of chemistry but also in geology and biology. These reactions serve as the fundamental basis for food and energy sources on our planet, as well as for essential processes such as combustion and respiration. Furthermore, molecules containing a redox-active moiety are frequently utilized in electrodes, batteries, and sensors, highlighting their widespread application in various technological fields. In the pursuit of achieving sustainable battery chemistry, continuous endeavors are being made to substitute transition metal-based electrode materials with redox-active organic materials (ROMs). The majority of ROMs consist of elements that are abundant in the Earth's crust, such as carbon, nitrogen, oxygen, and sulfur. As a result, they are not significantly limited by resource constraints, and their production does not necessitate energy-intensive processes.

Many ROMs, such as TEMPO, viologens, phenazines, thiazines and quinones have proven to serve as an alternative for metal-based redox systems, particularly in the context of electrodes and flow battery technology.^{1,2} The structural diversity and chemical tunability of these organic compounds make them highly appealing for the flexible design of forthcoming energy storage systems. Specifically, the quinone-hydroquinone couples have been extensively researched for several decades, dating back to the early 1900s.³ Molecular redesign of quinones enables precise tuning of the electrochemical performance in battery applications.^{4–10} The introduction of different functional groups enables a shifting of the redox potential as electron withdrawing or electron donating groups altering the HOMO-LUMO gap in such systems. The solubility of the molecules can be improved by attachment of ionic groups such as sulphonate, phosphonate, carboxyl, or amines. Substitution also prevents undesirable side reactions such as disproportionation, nucleophilic addition (e.g., gem-diol formation, Michael addition, and hydrolysis), dimerization/oligomerization, hydrogen bond formation/chemical transformations, and tautomerization. The main challenges in quinone-based ROMs comprise limited solubility in aqueous systems, stability during electrochemical cycling,^{11,12} and the availability of feedstock at large scale. Moreover, some quinones

are extremely toxic (e.g., benzoquinone) and pose risks to the environment.

A different class are aminoquinones which were reported to exhibit anti-inflammatory¹³ and anti-tumor^{14–16} activities. They have also been explored as materials for biobased insulation,¹⁷ optoelectronic devices, and batteries.^{18–20} However, the synthesis of aminoquinones can be challenging, and there is a need for simple and efficient routes to access these compounds. Many methods involve the use of metal catalysts or halogenated starting materials.²¹ It would be desirable to employ precursors derived from lignocellulosic waste, particularly lignin, a complex polyaromatic biopolymer produced at a large scale (ca. 100 Mt/a) in the pulp and paper industry for aminoquinone synthesis.²² Despite intense efforts in academia and industry, still the majority of lignin is incinerated (98%), with vanillin (4-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzaldehyde) being one of the few commercial fine chemicals produced from lignin on an industrial scale (ca. 15,000 t/a).²³ Previously reported approaches employed the use of *p*-benzoquinone as a starting material, which is toxic and more expensive than the vanillin precursor.^{24,25} There is only a single study where aminoquinones have been synthesized directly from vanillin but the resulting quinones were not investigated in terms of their electrochemical properties.²⁶ Thermochromic, polarographic and solvatochromic effects were reported for other selected compounds.^{27–29} In this work, we present the electrochemical properties of seven aminoquinones.

Experimental

Materials.—Vanillin (≥99%), *o*-H₃PO₄ (85%), potassium chloride (≥99%), sodium phosphate dibasic hydrate (≥99%), sodium phosphate monobasic dihydrate (≥99%), dimethyl amine solution (2.0 M in methanol), piperidine (≥99%), 2-(methylamino)ethanol (≥98%), methylamine solution (33 wt% in ethanol denaturated with toluene 1%), propylamine (≥99%), 1-methylpiperazine (≥99%) and *N*-methylcyclohexylamine (99%) were purchased from Merck KGaA (Darmstadt, Germany). Sodium acetate trihydrate (99.3%) was purchased from VWR International GmbH (Vienna, Austria). CDCl₃ (99.9%), DMSO-*d*₆ (99.8%) as well as D₂O (99.9%) were purchased from Eurisotop SAS (St. Aubin, France). 2-methoxyhydroquinone (98%) was prepared according to a literature procedure.³⁰

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Electrochemical measurements.—Cyclic voltammograms (CVs) were carried out using a BioLogic SP150 potentiostat/galvanostat using ECLab software. A VC4 Voltammetry cell (ALS Co.) with a glassy carbon working electrode (GCE; GC6x3, ALS Co., 3 mm diameter), a platinum wire as counter electrode and an Ag/AgCl (RE1B, 3 M NaCl, ALS Co.) reference electrode ($E_0 = 195$ mV vs SHE) was used.

The working electrode was polished using a 0.05 μm alumina polishing solution and polishing pad (PK3 Electrode Polishing kit, ALS Co.) prior to each measurement and a 1 μm diamond polishing solution if necessary. The electrolyte solutions were degassed by bubbling nitrogen through the solution for at least 10 min before measurement. Slight shifts in the redox potential of the same compound in different experiments are attributed to minor changes in the electrolyte composition. All CVs are found in Fig. S1. For the overview cyclic voltammogram recordings, about 3 mg of the compound were weighted in, suspended in 3 ml of the corresponding solvent and sonicated. For the Randles Sevcik analysis, the electrolyte solutions were prepared in 0.5 M H_3PO_4 . The compounds were dissolved in 3 ml of the corresponding solvent. A preliminary CV was conducted for each compound to determine the suitable voltage region, afterwards CVs with 5 scan rates (500; 200; 100; 50 and 20 mV s^{-1}) were conducted. The curve generated during the third cycle of each scan rate experiment was used for calculations. For the creation of the Pourbaix diagrams, different solutions were prepared. For the buffer solutions, the corresponding salts were placed in a 100 ml volumetric flask, dissolved in distilled water, and diluted to 100 ml. The alkaline solutions in the range of pH 9 to 14 were prepared by adjusting the pH of 0.5 M KCl with 1 M NaOH to the desired pH value. The exact weighted samples are given in Table S2. The data analysis was carried out using ECLab software by Biologic. Graphs were created using Origin data analysis software (OriginLab Corporation).

NMR spectroscopy.—The NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker Avance 300 MHz spectrometer. For the NMR experiments, 10–50 mg of the solid sample was diluted in 0.7 ml of deuterated solvent ($\text{DMSO-}d_6$ or CDCl_3). The samples were referenced vs TMS by using the internal ^2H lock signal of the solvent. The analysis of the spectra was performed using MNova (Mestrelab Research) software.

ATR-IR spectroscopy.—The ATR-IR spectra were recorded using a Bruker Alpha-P Diamond ATR spectrometer from the solid sample and visualized with OPUS spectroscopy software (Bruker). The analysis was performed using Origin data analysis software (OriginLab Corporation).

UV-vis spectroscopy.—The measurements were carried out with a Cary 60 UV-vis spectrometer (Agilent Technologies). Solutions with a concentration of 1×10^{-3} , 5×10^{-4} and 1×10^{-4} mol l^{-1} were prepared using acetonitrile as a solvent. For measurement, the solutions were filled in 1 $\text{cm} \times 1$ cm quartz cuvettes. The analysis was performed using Origin data analysis software (OriginLab Corporation).

Aqueous solubility tests.—Aqueous solubility tests were carried out in 0.5 M H_3PO_4 , deionized water and 1 M NaOH. A small amount of the respective compound was transferred into a glass vial containing the solvent (100–1000 μl depending on the estimated solubility). After the addition, the vial was shaken using a Vortex Generator and visually inspected. The addition of the compound was carried out until no further dissolution of the sample was realized. The solubility values are given in the supplementary material in Table S1.

X-Ray crystallography.—All crystals suitable for single crystal X-ray diffraction were removed from a vial and immediately covered with a layer of silicone oil. A single crystal was selected,

mounted on a glass rod on a copper pin, and placed in the cold N_2 stream provided by an Oxford Cryosystems cryostream. XRD data collection was performed for compounds **5**, on a Bruker APEX II diffractometer³¹ with use of an $\text{I}\mu\text{S}$ microsource (Incoatec micro-focus) sealed tube of Mo $\text{K}\alpha$ radiation ($\lambda = 0.71073$ Å) and a CCD area detector. The unit-cell constants and the orientation matrices were determined by the program CELL_NOW.³² Data integration was carried out using SAINT.³¹ Empirical absorption corrections were applied using SADABS.^{33,34} The structures were solved with use of the intrinsic phasing option in SHELXT³⁵ and refined by the full-matrix least-squares procedures in SHELXL^{35–39} as implemented in the program SHELXLE.⁴⁰ The space group assignments and structural solutions were evaluated using PLATON.^{41,42} Non-hydrogen atoms were refined anisotropically. Hydrogen atoms bonded to N or O for all compounds were located in a difference map. All other hydrogen atoms were located in calculated positions corresponding to standard bond lengths and angles and refined using a riding model. Electrostatic non-covalent intermolecular interactions (C—H... π) were determined by the programs Mercury⁴³ and Diamond⁴⁴ using the centroids and planes and other features of these programs. All crystal structure representations were made with the program Diamond⁴⁵ with all non-carbon atoms displayed as 30% ellipsoids. CCDC 2314233 contain the elementary crystallographic data for compound **5**. These data can be obtained free of charge from The Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre via www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/data_request/cif. CIF files were edited, validated and formatted either with the programs enCIFer,⁴⁶ publCIF,⁴⁷ or Olex2.⁴⁸ Tables S3–S9 contain crystallographic data and details of measurements and refinement for compound **5**.

DFT calculations.—Calculations were carried out with the Gaussian16 program package.⁴⁹ First, geometry optimizations of **1–7** were performed in gas phase at the B3LYP/6–31++G(d,p) level of theory.^{50–52} Harmonic frequencies were computed to confirm that the optimized geometries are minima at the potential energy surface and to get the Gibbs free energies. ^{13}C -NMR chemical shifts were calculated using the optimized gas phase structures using tetramethylsilane as the reference applying the C-PCM model of solvation for the respective solvents (CDCl_3 or DMSO) of the experimental NMR spectra. The calculation of the UV/VIS spectrum was performed by calculation of 15 vertical excitations applying time-dependent DFT (TD-DFT) with the long-range corrected CAM-B3LYP functional⁵³ and the 6-311+G(d,p) basis set in acetonitrile. The resulting HOMO-LUMO gaps were taken from these outputs. The rearranged conformations of quinone to quinol and the subsequent hydrolysis products were located at the M062X/6-311++G(d,p) level of theory in water, because this functional has small mean absolute deviations (MAD) for thermochemical properties.⁵⁴

Synthesis of the different aminoquinones.—**1–4** & **7**.—In a 100 ml round bottom flask, 80 ml of ethanol was stirred with vanillin (5 g, 45 mmol, 1 equiv.) for 15 min. An excess (3.2 equiv.) of the respective pure amine was added via syringe to the reaction mixture at 25 °C within 5 min. After addition, the solutions turned red and were stirred overnight. The formed precipitate was filtered off, and washed with ice-cold ethanol to obtain red crystals.

5 & **6**.—In a 100 ml round bottom flask, MHQ (5 g, 36 mmol, 1 equiv.) was dissolved in 80 ml ethyl acetate. 2 equiv. of methylamine or propylamine were added to the reaction mixture via syringe within 5 min and stirred at 25 °C for 24 h. After complete conversion, the solvent was stripped of using a rotary evaporator. The crude product was recrystallized in ethanol and stored in the fridge at 4 °C. The obtained red crystals were filtered off and washed using ice-cold ethanol.

Characterization of 1–7.—**2,5-Bis(dimethylamino)cyclohexa-2,5-diene-1,4-dione, 1**, dark-red solid, m.p: 170 °C–172 °C, yield,

65%, ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 5.35 (s, 2H, ring-*H*), 3.19 (s, 12H, N- CH_3), ^{13}C NMR (76 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 181.75 (C=O), 152.37 (C=C-N-), 102.13 (C=C-H), 42.82 (- CH_3), IR [cm^{-1}]: 2915 (C-H stretch), 1622 (C=O stretch), UV-vis: λ [nm] (ϵ [$\text{l mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$]): 486 (1760), 360 (1760).

2,5-Bis(*N*-methylethanolamino)cyclohexa-2,5-diene-1,4-dione, 2, dark-red solid, m.p.: 160 °C–162 °C, yield: 85%, ^1H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-d_6) δ 5.28 (s, 2H, ring-*H*), 4.74 (s, 2H, OH), 3.77 (t, $J = 5.4$ Hz, 4H, O- CH_2), 3.57 (t, $J = 5.4$ Hz, 4H, N- CH_2), 3.02 (s, 6H, CH_3), ^{13}C NMR (76 MHz, DMSO-d_6) δ 180.67 (C=O), 151.78 (C=C-N-), 101.24 (C=C-H), 59.41 (- CH_2 -OH), 55.73 (N- CH_2 -), 41.40 (- CH_3), IR [cm^{-1}]: 3303 (s, OH-stretch), 2930 (C-H stretch), 1612 (m, C=O stretch), UV-vis: λ [nm] (ϵ [$\text{l mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$]): 507 (640), 364 (52000).

2,5-Bis(piperidin-1-yl)cyclohexa-2,5-diene-1,4-dione, 3, violet-red solid, m.p.: 172 °C–175 °C, yield: 80%, ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 5.53 (s, 2H, ring-*H*), 3.53 (bs, 8H, N- CH_2), 1.66 (bs, 12H, other CH_2 groups in ring), ^{13}C NMR (76 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 182.70 (C=O), 153.36 (C=C-N-), 105.71 (C=C-H), 50.51 (N- CH_2 -), 26.03 (N- CH_2 - CH_2 -), 24.51 (N- CH_2 - CH_2 - CH_2 -), IR [cm^{-1}]: 2920 (C-H stretch), 1622 (m, C=O quinone stretch), UV-vis: λ [nm] (ϵ [$\text{l mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$]): 517 (62000), 372 (33000).

2,5-Bis(*N*-methylcyclohexylamino)cyclohexa-2,5-diene-1,4-dione, 4, brick-red solid, m.p.: 135 °C–137 °C, yield: 23%, ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 5.40 (s, 2H, quinone ring-*H*), 2.89 (s, 6H, N- CH_3), 1.80 (s, 4H, ring CH_2), 1.80 (s, 4H, ring CH_2), 1.77 (s, 4H, ring CH_2), 1.67 (d, $J = 12.8$ Hz, 3H, CH_3), 1.58–1.20 (m, 9H, ring CH_2), 1.20–0.99 (m, 3H), ^{13}C NMR (76 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 182.13 (C=O), 153.26 (C=C-N-), 102.87 (C=C-H), 59.90 (N-CH), 33.57 (N- CH_3), 30.48 (Cy), 25.72 (Cy), IR [cm^{-1}]: 2925 (C-H stretch), 1606 (m, C=O stretch), UV-vis: λ [nm] (ϵ [$\text{l mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$]): 508 (530), 370 (19400).

2,5-Bis(propylamino)cyclohexa-2,5-diene-1,4-dione, 5 dark-red solid, m.p.: 158 °C–160 °C, yield 80%, ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 6.67 (bs, 2H, NH), 5.31 (s, 2H, ring-*H*), 3.11 (q, $J = 6.8$ Hz, 4H, N- CH_2), 1.68 (s, $J = 7.1$ Hz, 4H, N CH_2 - CH_2), 0.99 (t, $J = 7.3$ Hz, 6H, CH_3), ^{13}C NMR (76 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 178.21 (C=O), 151.58 (C=C-NH), 92.74 (C=C-H), 44.34 (HN- CH_2 -), 21.66 (CH_2 - CH_3), 11.55 (- CH_3), IR [cm^{-1}]: 3282 (m, NH-stretch), 2930 (m, CH-stretch), 1556 (m, C=O quinone stretch), UV-vis: λ [nm] (ϵ [$\text{l mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$]): 483 (380), 333 (77000).

2,5-Bis(methylamino)cyclohexa-2,5-diene-1,4-dione, 6, dark-red solid, m.p.: 282 °C–285 °C (decomp.), yield: 75%, ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.84 (bs, 2H, NH), 5.14 (s, 2H, ring-*H*), 2.73 (d, $J = 5.2$ Hz, CH_3), ^{13}C NMR (76 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 177.21 (C=O), 152.41 (C=C-NH), 91.91 (C=C-H), 28.82 (- CH_3), IR [cm^{-1}]: 3281

(m, NH-stretch), 2949 (m, CH-stretch), 1644 (m, C=O quinone stretch), UV-vis: λ [nm] (ϵ [$\text{l mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$]): 478 (360), 331 (500).

2,5-Bis(4-methylpiperazine)cyclohexa-2,5-diene-1,4-dione, 7, red needles, mp.: 209 °C–211 °C, yield: 78%, ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 5.53 (s, 2H, ring-*H*), 3.56 (t, $J = 5.7$ Hz, 4H, C-N- CH_2), 2.50 (t, $J = 5.1$ Hz, 8H, CH_3 -N- CH_2), 2.30 (s, 6H, N- CH_3), ^{13}C NMR (76 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 182.85 (C=O), 152.70 (C=C-NH), 106.97 (C=C-H), 54.81 (CH_2 -N- CH_3), 48.84 (N- CH_2 -), 46.08 (- CH_3), IR [cm^{-1}]: 3037 (m, NH-stretch), 2944 (m, CH-stretch), 1631 (m, C=O quinone stretch), UV-vis: λ [nm] (ϵ [$\text{l mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$]): 509 (640), 366 (35000).

Results and Discussion

Synthesis and characterization of symmetric aminoquinones.—

We investigated seven compounds synthesized via the reaction of vanillin with a variety of secondary amines (Schemes 1 and 2).⁵⁵ The yields of this reaction strongly depend on the used amines and range from 75 to 85% for all amines, except *N*-methylcyclohexylamine. Sterically demanding amines generally result in lower yields. For example, *N*-methylcyclohexylamine has a bulky cyclohexane ring structure, which increases steric hindrance compared to linear amines like methylamine or dimethylamine. Moreover, the solubility and electronic effects can affect the yield of the reaction.

The reaction works particularly well for secondary, but not for primary amines. The reason is a competing reaction leading to Schiff base formation, which becomes predominant for primary amines. However, the exception is the reaction of methylamine with vanillin which led to the formation of Michael addition product **6** in 46% yield. The reaction of propylamine with vanillin, however, led almost exclusively to the formation of the Schiff-base adduct⁵⁶ (Scheme 1, bottom). The lower basicity of propylamine compared to methylamine and, therefore, higher acidity of the conjugated acid, catalyzes the formation of the imine.⁵⁷ Interestingly, the Michael addition-type product **5** could only be observed by reacting propylamine with *p*-benzoquinone⁵⁸ or using 2-methoxy hydroquinone (MHQ) as the starting material (75 and 70% yield, respectively).

The IR spectra show a broad absorption band at 3200–3500 cm^{-1} for compounds **2** (ν_{OH}) and **5** (ν_{NH}), confirming the proposed structure. Compound **6** exhibits a sharp ν_{NH} band at ca 3500 cm^{-1} typical for secondary amines in the solid state. A prominent band arises at around 1600 cm^{-1} , which is characteristic for a $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{O}}$ stretch. In this region, also the sharp $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{C}}$ bands of the quinone are visible. In the solid state, the compounds feature a deep red to purple color due to their azamethine structure (Scheme 1). The compounds

Scheme 1. Top: Reaction of secondary amines with vanillin yielding to Michael-type products. Bottom: Nucleophilic addition of primary amines and vanillin, forming an imine (Schiff-base type adduct).

Scheme 2. Molecular structures of the synthesized 2,5-substituted symmetric aminoquinones 1–7.

exhibit strong solvatochromism, making them appear dark yellow in acetonitrile.⁵⁹ The UV–vis spectra of the aminoquinones in acetonitrile show a λ_{max} between 331–372 nm in the UV and at 478–517 nm in the visible region. A $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition is expected to be symmetry-forbidden in the investigated compounds, but occurs as a band with low intensity, which is owed to the resonance hybrid form of aminoquinones. Its occurrence is caused by vibrational motion of the molecules, as the closely spaced HOMOs and LUMOs are mixing by participation of nuclear vibrations, also known as Herzberg-Teller effect.^{60,61} This causes the intensity of the allowed UV-transition to decrease in favor of the intensity of the forbidden VIS transition. For the quinones substituted with a secondary amine, the λ_{max} in the UV region are bathochromically shifted compared to the quinones bearing a primary amine as substituent. This effect is caused by the higher electron donating effect of the secondary amines, leading to a decrease in the HOMO-LUMO gap and a redshift in the UV–vis spectrum. The deshielding effect due to the higher electron-donating nature of the secondary amine substituents leads to a downfield shift in the carbon NMR spectrum.

The aminoquinones show large upfield shifts in the ^1H (δ : 5.14–5.53 ppm) and ^{13}C -NMR spectra (δ : 177.2–182.8 ppm) of the pseudoaromatic C–H-protons and carbons compared to *p*-benzoquinone (δ : 6.80 and 187.21 ppm for ^1H and ^{13}C -NMR spectra). This is a consequence of the strong polarization of the σ bonds by the presence of nitrogen, (+I effect), leading to higher basicity of the adjacent proton. The strongest effect is observed for 2

which has the highest upfield shift in the ^1H and 6 in the ^{13}C -NMR spectra. All compounds are obtained as crystals but only 5 gave suitable ones for single X-ray diffraction purposes. In the solid state, 5 adopts a sheet like structure that is formed by hydrogen bonding of the secondary amine protons with the quinone functionality (Fig. 1). The hydrogen bonds can be classified as strong according to Steiner⁶² (N1–H1...O1 distance: 2.064 (14) Å, N1...O1: 2.8694 (10) Å, N1–H1...O1 angle: 151.0 (13)°). The sheets are held together by CH contacts of the terminal CH_3 of the propyl group with the central aromatic rings. While the C=O bond lengths (C3–O1: 1.2449 (10) Å) correlate well with published data for *p*-benzoquinone (1.223 Å), the C–N bond to the aromatic rings is shorter (C1–N1: 1.3329 (10) Å) than the C–N bond to the propyl group (C4–N1: 1.4571 (11) Å). This indicates that aminoquinones and especially compound 5 occur in the form of mesomeric structures (Scheme 1) as the C1–N1 bond length resembles more an aromatic C–N single bond with a nearly planar amino nitrogen (C–N: 1.46 Å, $\text{C}_{\text{ar}}\text{--NH--C}$ with pyramidal N: 1.419 Å, $\text{C}_{\text{ar}}\text{--NH--C}$ with planar N: 1.353 Å, C=N: 1.21 Å⁶³).

The functional groups of the aminoquinones significantly affect crystal packing, which, in turn, can alter their electrochemical behaviour in solid state. Aminoquinones can form hydrogen bonds between amine (–NH) or hydroxyl groups (–OH), leading to a more ordered or tighter packing arrangement. Bulky groups on the amines might prevent efficient packing, creating looser crystal structures, which might lead to more free volume or structural defects. The

Figure 1. (a) ORTEP representation for compound 5. All non-carbon atoms shown as 30% shaded ellipsoids. Most hydrogen atoms omitted for clarity. Selected bond lengths [Å] with estimated standard deviations: C=O: 1.245 Å, C–N: 1.333 Å. (b) Crystal packing diagram for 5. Hydrogen bonding contacts and C–H... π interactions highlighted by dashed bonds. All non-carbon atoms shown as 30% shaded ellipsoids. Hydrogen atoms not involved in intermolecular interactions omitted for clarity.

Table I. λ_{\max} and molar extinction coefficients ϵ of 1–7. The TD-CAM-B3LYP/6–311++G(d,p)//B3LYP/6–31++G**/D3-BJ method was used in the solvent acetonitrile for the S₁ excitations, and the corresponding HOMO-LUMO gaps ($\Delta_{\text{H-L}}$) were employed. Experimental ¹³C NMR chemical shifts (δ_{exp}) of the carbonyl group are compared to theoretical data (δ_{DFT}) taken from a B3LYP/6–311+G* calculation in the respective solvent.

Compound	$\lambda_{\max, \text{UV}}$ [nm]	$\lambda_{\max, \text{Vis}}$ [nm]	$\lambda_{\text{DFT, Vis}}$ [nm]	$\Delta_{\text{H-L}}$ [eV]	ϵ_{UV}	ϵ_{Vis}	$\delta_{\text{exp}}^{13}\text{C}_{\text{C=O}}$ [ppm]	$\delta_{\text{DFT}}^{13}\text{C}_{\text{C=O}}$ [ppm]
1	360	486	474	5.51	1760	3200	181.8	177.9
2	364	507	497	5.41	52000	640	180.7	178.5
3	372	517	500	5.35	33000	62000	182.7	178.6
4	370	508	490	5.45	19400	530	182.1	178.4
5	333	483	455	5.70	77000	380	178.2	174.8
6	331	478	461	5.70	500	360	177.2	174.2
7	366	509	517	5.06	35000	640	182.9	177.8

arrangement of the molecules in the crystal structure directly impacts electron transfer processes, which are essential for the electrochemical behaviour. Closely packed crystals facilitate better electron transfer mobility, enhancing conductivity or redox behaviour. Efficient crystal packing also results in lower resistance for charge transfer, which is critical for redox reactions. When the aminoquinones are dissolved in e.g. aqueous media, the influence of the crystal packing diminishes, however, many of the same functional group effects that impact crystal packing can still influence solution-phase behaviour. In aqueous media, functional groups such as -NH and -OH can form hydrogen bonds with each other, altering how they interact in solution. Even though crystal packing no longer plays a role, certain functional groups can still promote aggregation or micelle formation in solution. Hydrophobic interactions between nonpolar regions or π - π stacking between aromatic rings could cause the aminoquinones to cluster together in water, which could affect their electrochemical behavior by limiting accessibility to the electrode surface. Water molecules interacting with the aminoquinones can stabilize different oxidation states (e.g., quinone vs hydroquinone forms) and impact the overall redox potential. Functional groups that influence how much water can solvate different parts of the molecule will affect the ease of redox reactions. In aqueous solution, the electrochemical behavior depends more on the diffusion of the aminoquinone molecules to the electrode surface. Functional groups that influence the molecule's size, polarity, or charge can affect diffusion rates. More polar or charged groups could improve diffusion in aqueous media due to better interaction with the solvent, while hydrophobic or bulky groups might slow it down. This all can e.g. affect the measured current of the compounds, as shown in Fig. 3a, where the current of compound **1** is higher than in compound **2**.

The prevalence of resonance structures motivated us to perform DFT calculations and to connect those to the properties of the compounds in terms of relative energy, HOMO-LUMO gap, UV band and NMR shifts (Table I). In general, the main challenges with such molecules are the presence of several conformers and radical species, requiring care for the localization of the global minimum. The geometry optimization for the quinones confirms the presence of the quinone resonance structures for all aminoquinones based on relative energy and as indicated by a shortened C_{aryl}-N bond, ranging from 1.332 to 1.356 Å. The lone pair of the amino nitrogen atoms donate into the pi-system and, this way, shortens this C_{aryl}-N single bond. The respective imine forms have much higher relative energies in the range of ca. 100 kJ mol⁻¹ for **5** and **6**, respectively, and are therefore not taken into account. On the contrary, the corresponding hydroquinones feature C_{aryl}-N bond lengths which are closer to C-N single bonds (1.385 to 1.431 Å), indicating a less pronounced resonance structure.

Further, the TD-DFT calculations show a good agreement with the experimental UV spectra, where the first band is in all molecules assigned to the HOMO→LUMO transition and shows a negligible oscillator strength (in most cases, $f = 0.000$). The main trend was that the calculated $\lambda_{\max, \text{vis}}$ are bathochromically shifted between 12 and 20 nm, with the only exception of **7**, where the calculated

$\lambda_{\max, \text{vis}}$ is slightly hypsochromically shifted caused by the fact that the S₁ transition in **7** has a high CT character (the excitation includes large contributions from piperazine into the quinone moiety) in contrast to the other molecules, which show more local excitations. The HOMO-LUMO gaps are in the range between 5.1 and 5.7 eV which is a typical value for quinones carrying electron donating substituents.⁶⁴ The calculated ¹³C-NMR shifts of the carbonyl-carbons are in good agreement with the experimental ones, having deviations between 2.2 and 5.0 ppm to the experimentally derived spectra. The secondary amines in compound **5** and **6** induce a lower downfield shift to the carbonyl carbon atoms compared to the tertiary amines as indicated by both experimental and computed values.

The physical properties of the aminoquinones play a crucial role in determining their effectiveness in electrochemical applications. Solubility directly affects diffusion rates and accessibility to the electrode surface, influencing the efficiency of redox reactions. The solubility of the compounds is strongly connected to the symmetry of the aminoquinone and the type of amine used for synthesis. Solubility in aqueous solution ranges from nearly insoluble (**1**, **5**, **6**) up to ca. 30 mg ml⁻¹ (**7**). In general, by increasing the size of the hydrophobic alkyl part, the amines become less water soluble. By using more hydrophilic amines such as *N*-methylethanolamine (**2**) and *N*-methylpiperazine (**7**), the solubility in water can be increased (Table S1). The lower p_{Ka} values of both **2** and **7** (**2** = 9.95 and **7** = 9.14, other compounds = 10.49–11.12) indicate a higher tendency to donate electrons and increase hydrophilicity.⁶⁵

Electrochemistry.—Hydroquinone (H₂Q) can undergo a reversible oxidation to *p*-benzoquinone (pBQ) in acidic aqueous media through a single-step process that involves exchanging two electrons and two protons.⁶⁶ In contrast, in aprotic media, pBQ undergoes two consecutive reversible one e⁻ reduction reactions that produce a radical anion (pBQ^{•-}) and dianion (pBQ²⁻) by exchanging a total of two electrons.⁶⁷ To compare compounds **1–7** to the H₂Q-pBQ redox system, cyclic voltammetry (CV) measurements were conducted in aqueous media at different pH values and in acetonitrile using tetraethylammonium tetrafluoroborate as a supporting electrolyte. CV measurements were chosen as the preferred characterization technique, because rotating disc experiments (RDE) showed no plateau in the Levich study, due to sluggish kinetics. Additionally, reactions occurring within the diffusion layer of the electrode, particularly under extreme pH conditions, hindered the use of RDE for characterization.

In aprotic solvents, pBQ shows two reversible redox couples corresponding to two one-electron redox couples due to the stepwise formation of a mono- and a bianion radical (Fig. 2).⁶⁸ However, for **1** and **2**, the shift between the two steps is smaller (160 and 190 mV) as it is the case for pBQ (500 mV). For some compounds, e.g., for **3**, the second redox process is completely inexistent. As described by Bayen et al.,⁶⁹ the second electron transfer process in diaminoquinones is more difficult to accomplish, because the di-anion is not favored in an aromatic ring system that has two electron-donating amine functionalities. In addition, the di-anion of 1,4-benzoquinones is also proton-sensitive and the labile protons in these systems affect

Figure 2. CVs of compounds 1–3 measured under protic (0.5 M H₃PO₄) and aprotic (acetonitrile + 1 mmol ml⁻¹ TEABF₄) conditions. The measurement of *p*-benzoquinone is given as reference. The CVs were recorded at 5 different scan rates (500, 200, 100, 50 and 20 mV s⁻¹).

the second redox process. In diaminoquinones, there is already a source for labile protons, which disfavors di-anion formation.

In protic solvents, 1,4-benzoquinone is reduced to 1,4-hydroquinone following a 2e⁻, 2H⁺ reaction, showing one oxidation and one reduction peak in the cyclic voltammograms (Fig. 2). Because the reduction of the quinone in aqueous solution requires a source of protons, in the absence of a buffer, this leads to an increase in the pH value near the electrode, influencing the recorded potential of the quinone.⁷⁰ Therefore, all CVs were carried out in buffered media (for preparation of solution, see Table S2). Compound 2 can possibly show two redox active species in acidic, aqueous solution as a result of a quinone-quinol equilibrium as found for the monosubstituted compound.^{27,28,71} The quinols are formed by the addition of the hydroxy group of the amino moiety to the carbonyl group adjacent to the amino-group. The mono-substituted 1,4-benzoquinone (R = 2-N(CH₃)CH₂CH₂OH) has a reported tautomeric equilibrium constant (K = [Q]/[C]) of 0.063 with half-wave potentials of (E₀)₁ = -0.08 V and (E₀)₂ = -0.92 V vs SHE at pH 7.0. For the di-substituted compound 2, a half-wave potential of E₀ = -0.09 V vs SHE was reported for pH 7.0. There was no second redox species observed, which is in accordance to our measurements of 2 (E₀ = -0.086 V) at the same pH-level. However, the measurement of the peak current of the second wave must be obtained by using the decaying current of the first wave as a baseline (Fig. S1).⁷² After prolonged storage, 2 undergoes hydrolysis⁷³ (Scheme 3) which results in a change of color from red to brown in solution. This process was also observed for the other compounds (Fig. S28). DFT calculations on the quinone-quinol equilibrium showed a thermodynamically endothermic Gibbs free energy for the rearrangement into the quinol, making it highly unlikely to be present at pH 7. Hydrolysis of 2 is also energetically disfavored, therefore, we assume that only the quinone form is present at pH 7. This is different to the mono-substituted compound.

The E₀ values are strongly influenced by the substituent on the quinone. It is expected that there is a correlation between the 1 e⁻ and 2 e⁻/2 H⁺ reduction potentials.⁷⁴ Therefore, higher 1 e⁻

potentials should also lead to higher 2 e⁻/2 H⁺ potentials, which, however, does not correlate with the measured data (Table II). Substituent effects such as hydrogen bonding or steric effects can either lower or increase the 1 e⁻ or 2 e⁻/2 H⁺ reduction potentials.

In the *i*-*E* curves (cyclic voltammograms, CVs), two important parameters can be measured: the ratio of peak currents, *i*_{red}/*i*_{ox}, and the peak separation, E_{red}-E_{ox}, or ΔE_p. For a Nernstian (reversible) system, *i*_{red}/*i*_{ox} = 1, independent of the scan rate. ΔE_p is expected to be 59/*n* mV at 25 °C for an ideal Nernstian system.⁷²

The CVs were measured at different pH values. In phosphoric acid, ΔE_p of 1 is at 333 mV vs SHE with a peak-to-peak separation ΔE_p of 346 mV (at a scan rate of 100 mV s⁻¹). In KCl solution, the potential is shifted to negative direction to -89 mV vs SHE (ΔE_p = 80 mV), at an alkaline pH to -398 mV vs SHE (ΔE_p = 75 mV). The cyclovoltammograms indicate that compounds 1–7 are stable at acidic conditions, at least in the time scale of cyclic voltammetry. The investigated aminoquinones decompose in strongly acidic and alkaline solutions after several days, as indicated by the decoloration of the samples. Under basic conditions, quinones are highly reactive toward nucleophilic species, particularly hydroxide ions (OH⁻). The carbonyl groups (C=O) in the quinone structure are electrophilic, making them susceptible to attack by these nucleophiles. The OH⁻ ion attacks the carbon atom in the carbonyl group, leading to the formation of a tetrahedral intermediate. This intermediate is often unstable and can undergo further transformations, resulting in structural modifications. These transformations can irreversibly change the structure, reducing its electrochemical activity and altering its redox properties. Moreover, the quinone reduction to hydroquinone can be followed by side reactions, such as the formation of superoxide radicals (O₂⁻) when the hydroquinone reacts with oxygen. These radicals can initiate further reactions that lead to the formation of polymeric species or cross-linked structures. At low pH-levels, quinones can undergo hydrolysis reactions, where the carbonyl group reacts with water molecules. The acidic environment may also facilitate over-reduction of the quinone, causing electron transfer reactions that generate unstable intermediates. These intermediates can undergo condensation

Scheme 3. Quinone-quinol equilibrium of **2** and product of hydrolysis. Calculations of the relative Gibbs free energies (ΔG , relative to the lowest A2 energy conformer) were performed at the M062X/6-311++G(d,p) level of theory.

Table II. Electrochemical data of compounds **1–7** in protic^a (0.5 M H₃PO₄, 2e⁻/2 H⁺ reduction potential) and in aprotic conditions^b (acetonitrile, 1 e⁻ reduction potential).

Compound	2 e ⁻ /2 H ⁺ E ₀ [V] vs SHE ^[a]	1e ⁻ E ₀ [V] vs SHE ^[b]	I _{red} /I _{ox}	ΔE_p [V]	D _{0,ox} [cm ² s ⁻¹] × (10 ⁻⁶)	D _{0,red} [cm ² s ⁻¹] × (10 ⁻⁶)
1	0.333	-0.791	2.18	0.346	0.342	2.34
2	0.394	-0.714	1.16	0.105	0.169	0.234
3	0.496	-0.677	1.04	0.405	4.69	3.31
4	0.429	-0.819	0.879	0.246	0.0031	0.0021
5	0.314	-0.773	0.877	0.206	0.210	0.167
6	0.427	-0.777	0.625	0.101	0.066	0.039
7	0.368	-0.472	1.26	0.105	0.302	0.412

or dimerization, resulting in complex polymeric structures or irreversible by-products. Moreover, water molecules can be added to the ring system by Michael Addition reactions, influencing the reduction potential of the quinones.

As visible in Fig. 3a, **1** shows two oxidation and only one reduction peak at pH 1.2. In neutral solution, the reduction and oxidation of **1** yield one single peak in each direction, while there are additional peaks visible in alkaline solution. One explanation for the differing electrochemistry at pH 14 is that the solution shows discoloration shortly after dissolution in 1 M NaOH indicating decomposition (Fig. 3b). The additional peaks in the alkaline pH range could be attributed to degradation products.

The peak-to-peak separation at acidic and neutral pH-values is higher than expected at 340 mV and 200 mV, respectively. In a reversible redox process involving quinones, it is crucial for their peak separation to be smaller than 29.5 mV due to the principle of the Nernstian equation.⁷² The higher separation at acidic pH levels suggests the transfer of only 1 electron or quasi-reversible processes with sluggish kinetics.

A series of CVs at scan rates between 500 and 20 mV s⁻¹ was conducted for a more detailed investigation (SI, Fig. S2). A broadening of the distance between the reduction and oxidation peak is visible, with the peak-to-peak separation increasing from 338 mV at $\nu = 20$ mV s⁻¹ to 360 mV at 500 mV s⁻¹. The separation of peak and half-peak potential $\Delta E_{p,p/2}$ for a reversible two electron reaction would be expected to be 29.5 mV, the obtained values are significantly higher (101–346 mV). However, the formal redox potential is independent of the scan rate. This, as well as the increasing ΔE_p , supports the assumption of a quasi-reversible two

electron transfer, as opposed to a one electron transfer. This is in accordance with published data for similar 2,5-substituted aminoquinones.^{75,76} Compound **2** shows two oxidation and reduction peaks at acidic pH-values, as the compound exists in a quinone/quinol form, and with growing acidity, the equilibrium is shifted to the quinol form. At a neutral pH, the quinone form is predominant, leading to the observation of a single oxidation and reduction peak. At pH 14, the CV shows additional peaks and broadening at lower potential, indicating the formation of side products. This can be observed for all compounds at alkaline pH levels, with **3–5** and **7** showing the highest broadening and indistinct peaks. Compound **7** shows the highest reversibility at acidic conditions (see Fig. S3) with a peak-to-peak separation of 0.105 V and one distinct oxidation and reduction peak. ΔE_p is higher at neutral pH with 0.202 V. For compounds **4–6** a second reduction peak is visible at acidic conditions. Depending on the rate constant for each electron transfer step, which is also influenced by the medium, it might be possible that the electron transfers appear as two separate or one single wave.

Randles Sevcik analysis and Pourbaix plot.—The Randles–Sevcik equation describes that the peak current i_p (A) increases linearly with the square root of the scan rate ν (V s⁻¹), with n being the number of electrons transferred, A (cm²) being the active area of the electrode, D (cm² s⁻¹) is the diffusion coefficient, and c (mol cm⁻³) is the bulk concentration of the electroactive species.

$$i_p = 0.4463 n F A c \left(\frac{n F \nu D}{RT} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad [1]$$

Figure 3. (a) CVs (scan rate: 100 mV s^{-1} and $c = 1 \text{ mg ml}^{-1}$) of **1** (left) and **2** (right) as a function of pH value. (b) Photos of solutions of **2** at different pH levels after storage for 2 days (from left to right: pH 1.2, 3, 5, 7, 8, 9, 12 and 14). The discoloration at pH 14 was observed within a few minutes after dissolution and pH adjustment.

Figure 4. (a) Randles-Sevcik plot of **2** in $0.5 \text{ M H}_3\text{PO}_4$ (pH 1.23) with $c \approx 1 \text{ mg ml}^{-1}$ (3.9 mM). Peak currents are depicted vs the square root of the scan rate for 5 scan rates from 500 to 20 mV s^{-1} . (b) E_0 of **2** as a function of pH value at a scan rate of 100 mV s^{-1} . At more alkaline pH values, no defined oxidation and reduction peaks could be observed and are therefore excluded from the plot. Concentration: $\approx 1 \text{ mg ml}^{-1}$ (3.9 mM).

For a linear correlation with a zero intercept of the plot of i_p vs $\nu^{1/2}$, suggesting a complete agreement with the linear diffusion based diffusion model,⁷⁷ the fit can be used for an estimation of the diffusion coefficient using the slope of (Eq. 2):

$$D = \left(\frac{k}{2.69 \cdot 10^5 \cdot A \cdot C \cdot n^2} \right)^2 \quad [2]$$

With k being the slope of the linear regression line of the Randles-Sevcik plot [$\text{A} \cdot (\text{V s}^{-1})^{-1/2}$], $k = i_p \cdot \nu^{-1/2}$.

All compounds exhibit, at faster scan rates, an increase in the observed currents due to a decrease in the dimensions of the diffusion layer.⁷² Plots of the peak currents vs the square root of the scan rate of all compounds are given in Fig. S4. As a typical

example, **2** is depicted in Fig. 4a, yielding good linear correlations for both reduction and oxidation peak currents despite the quasi-reversibility of the system indicated by the shift of the peak potentials.

The linear correlation with the square root of the scan rate as opposed to the scan rate by itself indicates that the electron transfer occurs as a freely diffusing species. The peak current ratio I_{pa}/I_{pc} for **1–7** is given in Table II. The linear relationship between the limiting current and the square root of the scan rate demonstrates that the quinone reduction is a diffusion-controlled process. The diffusion coefficients (D in $\text{cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$) were obtained from Randles-Sevcik analysis (Eq. 1) and are summarized in Table II. The diffusion coefficients for all compounds except **3** are much lower than in the expected range for quinones (e.g., $5.03 \times 10^{-6} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ for hydroquinone).⁷⁸

To determine the heterogeneous standard rate constant k^0 , the well-known procedure proposed by Nicholson including the parameter Ψ (Eq. 3) can be used if ΔE_p does not exceed 200 mV (with $\Psi \approx 0.1$), which is the case for compounds **2**, **6** and **7**.⁷² The calculated values for k^0 (**2**: 1.07×10^{-3} , **6**: 2.15×10^{-3} , **7**: 1.57×10^{-3} cm 2 s $^{-1}$) are in the range of values found in literature for quinones (cf. 2,7-AQDS 7.2×10^{-3} cm 2 s $^{-1}$).⁷²

$$\Psi = \left(\frac{\pi D n \nu F}{RT} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad [3]$$

The redox reaction of many organic redox species, including quinones, involves protons and therefore exhibits strong pH dependence.⁷⁹ The shift of the redox potential with pH at a temperature of 25 °C can be described by Eq. 3,3a, with m being the number of protons and n the number of electrons involved in the redox reaction.

$$\Delta E = -\frac{m}{n} * 0.59 \text{ pH} \quad [3a]$$

The creation of a Pourbaix plot by recording CVs in different buffered media (see Fig. S5) can be used to estimate the ratio of protons and electrons involved in the redox reaction. As shown in Eq. 2, a shift of 59 mV/pH for a two-electron, two-proton reaction and a shift of 29.5 mV/pH for a two-electron, one-proton reaction can be expected. As an example, the Pourbaix plot of **2** is depicted in Fig. 4b, showing the increase of ΔE_p at neutral and near neutral pH levels. According to Eq. 2, the voltammogram shifts to more negative potentials with the increasing pH of the solution. The experimental slope obtained for **2** is 82 mV/pH unit, which is significantly higher than 29.5 mV/pH unit and likely corresponds to a two-electron, one-proton reaction. The other compounds are in the same range, with 61 mV s $^{-1}$ being the lowest (**5**) and 156 mV s $^{-1}$ the highest (**6**). For all compounds, the alkaline pH values at 12 and 14 were excluded from the plots as there was no linearity given. This may be caused by the fast degradation of the compounds in solution.

Conclusions

A series of 2,5-substituted aminoquinone species have been synthesized and electrochemically tested under protic and aprotic conditions. In protic media, they were measured at different pH-levels and show a quasi-reversible two-electron transfer. In aprotic conditions, the aminoquinones show two one-electron transfers, with the second transfer being more difficult due to the electron donating amine functionalities. The obtained data (E_0 , I_{red}/I_{ox} , ΔE_p and diffusion coefficients) add to the base of knowledge about quinones and their electrochemical properties, as well as their possible applications beyond areas already utilized.

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